

Foundations of Plasma Physics: A Mini Compendium

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Atomic physics basics

All matter consists of molecules and molecules consist of atoms. An atom is the smallest particle of a chemical element that determines its chemical properties. The structure of the atom: in the center of the atom there is a positive nucleus and it is surrounded by electrons that move around the nucleus in discrete energy levels (the Rutherford's theory).

Figure 1 – A composition of atom (according to Rutherford)
Nuclei itself consists of positive charged particles protons and neutrons with no charge (they are called nucleons). In their turn, nucleons consist in quarks

Figure 2 - The structure of protons and neutrons (a proton consists of uud quarks, a neutron consists of udd quarks, where u is an up quark, d is a down quark)

Rutherford's planetary model of the atom gave a good idea of the structure of the atom, but it had two problems.:

1. An atom should be unstable, when a charged particle, an electron, rotates around the nucleus, it creates an electromagnetic field, losing energy, over time it should fall on the nucleus, but this does not happen.

2. Rutherford's model did not explain the spectrum of an atom. According to Rutherford's theory, the spectrum should be continuous, but in fact, the spectrum was linear when the atom was heated or excited (only of certain wavelengths).

The solution to this problem is the Bohr model. Bohr's Postulates:

1. electrons can only move through certain rarefied levels, being on them they do not emit energy;
2. an atom emits when electrons move from a higher energy level to a lower one.

Figure 3 - Energy levels of electrons inside an atom (according to Bohr)

What is plasma

Plasma is an ionized gas consisting of free electrons and positive and negative ions, it is often referred to as the fourth state of matter. Plasma research is important primarily in energy and astrophysics. Plasma is used to create thermonuclear fusion, a reaction occurring in the Sun.

Converting to Joules: one gram of a deuterium–tritium mixture can give $3,4 \cdot 10^{11}$ J of energy, for comparison, 1 gram of oil gives $42 \cdot 10^3$ J. In addition, the world's fuel reserves are depleted every day: oil will last for about 70 years, natural gas for ~ 50 years, coal for ~ 125 years. Therefore, we need a new type of energy besides atomic energy.

In addition, since stars, the solar wind, and the interstellar medium are filled with plasma, astrophysics also studies plasma.

Plasma can be obtained from almost any material, if you transfer enough energy to it, gases are best suited – argon, neon, xenon, hydrogen, helium, nitrogen, air.

In nature, plasma is found on the Sun and other stars, lightning, and auroras. In technologies, for example, for TOKAMAKS, plasma is created by ionizing gases: heating, electric discharge, laser plasma creation, microwave plasma creation.

Heating: the gas heats up, the kinetic and potential energy of the atoms increases, electrons leave the atoms and become free electrons, the atoms, in turn, become ions, plasma is formed.

Electric discharge: a strong electric current passes through a gas, an electric field accelerates electrons, electrons collide with atoms, knocking out other electrons, ionization occurs, plasma is formed.

Laser plasma creation: a very powerful laser focuses on matter, energy is transferred to atoms, electrons become free, ionization occurs, plasma is formed.

Microwave plasma creation: the electromagnetic field accelerates electrons, they collide with atoms, creating ions, plasma is formed.

Figure 4 – The structure of plasma (electrons and ions)

Plasma parameters

The main properties of plasma are quasi-neutrality, electrical conductivity, collective particle behavior, charge shielding, and plasma oscillations.

Quasi-neutrality - plasma is generally electrically neutral, since the number of electrons is equal to the number of positive ions $n_e \approx n_i$, charges can be generated locally that form electric fields and currents, but on a large scale plasma is considered electro-neutral.

Figure 5 - Plasma quasi-neutrality

Electrical conductivity – plasma consists of charged particles, so plasma has good electrical conductivity and can react to electromagnetic fields. Therefore, plasma can be controlled using electromagnetic fields.

Collective behavior – in plasma, particles interact through electric and magnetic fields, unlike, for example, gases, where particles interact through collisions. Hence the collective effects – plasma waves, turbulence, instabilities.

Debye shielding is a phenomenon in which, when a charge is placed in a plasma, the particles around it rearrange and weaken its field. The characteristic size is the Debye length λ_D . At distances less than this radius, the surrounding particles cannot fully compensate for the charge, and at a distance greater than the Debye length, the field of the initial charge weakens.

Plasma oscillations are a phenomenon of collective oscillations of electrons relative to ions.

The frequency of these oscillations:
$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{n_e \cdot e^2}{\epsilon_0 \cdot m_e}}$$

where n_e is the electron density,

e is the electron charge,

m_e is the electron mass,

ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity.

The difference between cold and hot plasma

Hot plasma is plasma in which the temperature of electrons, ions, and neutral particles is the same ($T_e \approx T_i \approx T_n$ is in thermodynamic equilibrium) and is equal to millions of kelvin. Thermonuclear fusion plants reach temperatures of $\sim 10^7 \div 10^8$ K. Such plasma is found in the Sun and other stars, in thermonuclear installations (in tokamaks), in lightning, during nuclear explosions.

Cold plasma is a plasma in which the temperature of ions and neutral particles is significantly lower than the temperature of electrons ($T_e \gg T_i \approx T_n$). The

temperature of the electrons reaches $\sim 10^4 \div 10^5$ K, while the temperature of ions and neutral particles is approximately equal to room temperature (~ 300 K). This happens because electrons, being light, heat up quickly and are accelerated by an electric field, but they do not transfer energy well to heavy ions. It is used in plasma lamps and plasma medicine.

Plasma confinement

Electron plasma oscillations - plasma consists of ions and negatively charged electrons, if the electrons shift slightly, local electric fields are formed – areas with excess and deficiency of electrons. The electric field tends to bring the electrons back, and an oscillatory process begins due to inertia. It resembles a spring, where an electric field acts instead of the elastic force.

Ion acoustic waves – ions oscillate, and electrons are redistributed and create an electric field. This process resembles a sound wave.

The propagation velocity of such waves: $v_s = \sqrt{\frac{k \cdot T_e}{m_i}}$,

where T_e is the electron temperature,

m_i is the mass of the ion,

k is the Boltzmann constant, $k = 1,38 \cdot 10^{-23} \frac{J}{K}$.

The presence of a magnetic field changes the behavior of particles, as the Lorentz force acts on particles from the magnetic field:

$$\vec{F} = \vec{B} \cdot \vec{v} \cdot q.$$

This force causes the particle to gyrate around magnetic field lines. The radius of this circle is called the Larmor radius:

$$r_L = \frac{m \cdot v_{\perp}}{q \cdot B},$$

Where v_{\perp} is the velocity across the magnetic field,

B – magnetic field strength.

If there is also a velocity along the field, then the particle rotates in a helical trajectory

with a frequency of $\omega_c = \frac{q \cdot B}{m}$.

Figure 6 - The spiral trajectory of the particle motion, in the presence of transverse and longitudinal velocities

Accordingly, without a magnetic field, electron and ion oscillations occur in the plasma; in the presence of a magnetic field, Alfvén and cyclotron waves appear.

Plasma is an urgent research topic at the present time. The main problem is plasma confinement, since it has a temperature of several million Kelvin, it is impossible to maintain such a temperature with existing materials, therefore, the idea of plasma retention using magnetic fields, without contact with the walls of the reactor, was proposed.

As already mentioned, in the presence of a magnetic field, particles move in Larmor orbits, with a radius $r_L = \frac{m \cdot v_{\perp}}{q \cdot B}$, and movement along the field prevails compared to movement across the field, that is, the magnetic field restricts the movement of the plasma. The basic idea is: $r_L \ll L$, L is the size of the plasma. Then the particles move around the magnetic lines and cannot escape from the plasma. Moreover, in order for the plasma not to escape along the magnetic lines, they must be enclosed in a ring, therefore, a complex system of toroidal and poloidal magnetic fields is used for magnetic confinement.

Tokamak (toroidal chamber with magnetic coils) is an installation for plasma retention. The plasma there has the shape of a torus, hence the name. A toroidal field is created by coils around the chamber, a current flows through the plasma, this current creates a poloidal field. In this way, spiral magnetic lines are created along which particles move.

Figure 7 – Tokamak

A *stellarator* is an installation for magnetic plasma confinement, the main difference from a tokamak is that magnetic fields are created by external coils, that is, current in the plasma is not needed.

Figure 8 – Stellarator

Plasma is an unstable system because it contains free charged particles, conducts current, interacts with magnetic fields, and has high temperatures and pressures. Therefore, small instabilities can lead to turbulence, disruption of the plasma column, and loss of energy.

The main types of plasma instabilities are kink instability (bending of the plasma cord), sausage instability (compression and expansion of plasma), drift instability (temperature gradients), and magnetohydrodynamic instability (interaction of plasma and magnetic field).

Thermal stabilization of plasma is related to the distribution of temperature and pressure inside the plasma.

$$p = n \cdot k \cdot T,$$

where n is the particle concentration,

k is the Boltzmann constant,

T is the plasma temperature.

The methods of stabilization are uniform heating, density control.

Magnetic stabilization – magnetic fields control the movement of particles, thereby preventing the occurrence of disturbances in the plasma.

The term *plasma beta* is introduced to describe plasma stability:

$$\beta = \frac{2 \cdot \mu_0 \cdot p}{B^2},$$

where p is the plasma pressure,

B is the magnetic field induction,

μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of free space, $\mu_0 = 1,26 \cdot 10^{-6}$ H/m.

In a tokamak, $\beta \approx 0.1 \div 0.2$ – at such values, plasma is well retained by magnetic fields.

Laser-plasma interactions

Lasers are used to create plasma: the laser transfers energy to matter, as a result of which electrons are heated, atoms are ionized and plasma is formed.

Laser plasma generation: with such plasma formation, its density may be too high or too low, and the concept of critical density n_{cr} is introduced here. If a low-density plasma is used, which has a density less than n_{cr} , then the laser passes through the plasma with virtually no interaction and no plasma effects occur. If a high-density plasma is used, the electrons on the surface begin to shield the electromagnetic field of the laser and the beam cannot penetrate deep into the plasma, its intensity decreases, the beam is reflected. Therefore, materials with near-critical density are used - low-density foams. When the laser interacts with such a material, the beam easily ionizes the foam, penetrating deep into the material and creating a plasma.

Plasma diagnostics

Plasma diagnostic devices – Langmuir probe, plasma spectroscopy, interferometry.

A *Langmuir probe* is an electrode that is placed in a plasma to measure plasma density, electron temperature, and plasma potential.

Figure 9 - Langmuir probe

Plasma spectroscopy – electrons in plasma collide with atoms, transfer energy to them, the atoms go into an excited state, when they return to their normal state, they emit photons with energy $h\nu$, so a spectrum with lines of certain wavelengths appears. Plasma is analyzed using this spectrum – plasma composition, temperature, particle velocity, and density.

Figure 10 - Plasma spectroscopy

Plasma interferometry – the laser passes through the plasma, the plasma changes the refractive index and this change can be used to judge the electron density of the plasma. There is a reference beam that does not pass through the plasma, and a diagnostic beam that passes through the plasma. Next, the displacement of the diagnostic beam relative to the reference beam is analyzed.

Figure 11- Plasma interferometry

Current research challenges

The main directions related to plasma:

Controlled thermonuclear fusion - obtaining energy from a fusion reaction:

The main problems are plasma confinement, plasma instability, and damage to the reactor walls.

Currently, the ITER and JET projects are engaged in the implementation of this task. ITER is the largest international fusion experiment based in France. The reactor uses a tokamak, and the plasma is heated to 150 million Kelvins. It is planned to achieve an energy coefficient of $Q = 10$, where

$$Q = \frac{\text{fusion energy}}{\text{expended energy}}$$

Figure 12 – ITER

JET tokamak, which operated in the UK, worked with deuterium-tritium plasma. JET set a world record by receiving 69 MJ of energy from a plasma lasting 6 seconds. This tokamak also revealed the most suitable materials for the walls – tungsten and beryllium, which are now used in ITER.

Plasma instabilities – turbulence, magnetohydrodynamic instabilities. The task is to learn how to control these instabilities in order to ensure stable magnetic confinement of the plasma.

Laser-plasma interaction is the formation of plasma when a powerful laser interacts with matter. The problem is the selection of a material with a near-critical density to ensure effective interaction without energy loss.

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